

THE ISSUE OF EDUCATION IN SADRIDDIN AYNI'S "QIZ BOLA YOXUD XOLIDA"

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Abstract. This article provides a scientific and theoretical analysis of the issue of education in Sadriiddin Ayni's novel "Qiz bola yoxud Xolida".

Keywords: S. Ayni, pedagogue, quality, children, knowledge, improvement, good morals, character development, extracurricular activities, etc.

ПРОБЛЕМА ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В РОМАНЕ САДРИДДИНА АЙНИ «КИЗ БОЛА ЁХУД ХОЛИДА»

Аннотация. В статье дается научно-теоретический анализ проблемы образования в романе Садриддина Айни «Киз бола ёхуд Холида».

Ключевые слова: С. Айни, педагог, качество, дети, знания, совершенствование, нравственность, воспитание характера, внеклассная работа и т. д.

The protagonist of the novel is Xolida, the only child of the wealthy Mahmudboy family.

Initially, Xolida is unaware of literacy, good manners, or the beauty of life. She adorns herself with expensive clothes, jewelry, and decorations, looking down on other girls. Here, the author illustrates how improper family upbringing can lead to negative character traits in children.

According to Ayni, Xolida's parents spoiled her excessively, never opposing her whims, which led to her becoming selfish and arrogant.

To emphasize this idea, Ayni contrasts Xolida's character with that of another girl, Fotima, who is raised in the family of Ortiq Mashkob. Fotima, a diligent and well-mannered student, wears modest yet clean clothing and focuses on her studies. When Xolida boasts about her luxurious silk and velvet garments, Fotima disregards it and continues reading from a book, inviting Xolida to join her. However, since Xolida has never attended school, she is unable to read. Embarrassed, she returns home in tears and asks her parents to send her to school.

Even after enrolling in school, Xolida initially continues her habit of boasting about her clothes, preventing her from absorbing lessons effectively. However, observing her classmates' diligence and their indifference to material wealth gradually influences her. Over time, as the novel progresses, Xolida undergoes a dynamic transformation, evolving into the ideal, virtuous heroine that the author envisions.

Chapters such as "Xolida desires nothing but literacy", "Literacy and knowledge are not for sale in the market", "Xolida goes to school", and "Xolida removes her silk and velvet clothes"

illustrate her growing discipline, commitment to learning, and development of positive traits that make her a role model for others.

Ayni masterfully portrays the mutability of children's characters and the influence of their environment—especially school, peers, and teachers—in shaping their moral and intellectual development. He highlights the significance of extracurricular activities, such as properly organized recess breaks, in fostering good manners and moral values among children.

For example, in the chapters *"The Sheep and the Lamb"* and *"The Sheep Sacrifices Its Life for Its Lamb"*, the importance of storytelling and moral fables during break times is emphasized. After hearing the fable *"The Sheep and the Lamb"*, Xolida develops a deeper appreciation for her mother and begins to respect her parents' advice, realizing that their guidance is always in her best interest.

Ayni places significant emphasis on practical education, particularly in labor and handicrafts. In the novel, the teacher dedicates several hours a week to teaching crafts such as paper cutting and creating designs. Xolida actively participates in these lessons and quickly learns to sew. Within a year, she becomes skilled enough to sew not only her own clothes but also those of her parents. Eventually, even her neighbors entrust her with sewing their garments.

This demonstrates Ayni's perspective that education should not be limited to reading and writing but should also equip students with practical skills that can be applied in real life. The chapters *"Xolida Learns Handicrafts"*, *"Xolida Sews Clothes"*, and *"Xolida's Daily Routine"* emphasize the importance of integrating education with practical experience.

Through effective schooling and moral guidance, Xolida transforms from a spoiled and arrogant girl into a humble, hardworking, and compassionate citizen. This transformation is vividly illustrated in chapters such as *"Xolida's Morals and Habits"*, *"Xolida's Life at School"*, and *"Xolida Saves a Squirrel from Death"*.

The chapter *"Xolida's Daily Routine"* describes her structured daily activities. Although the schedule presented in the book may not be theoretically perfect, it serves as a practical guideline for students of that era, making their daily lives more organized and efficient.

In addition, the novel criticizes superstition and irrational beliefs. Chapters such as *"Superstition"*, *"A Story About Superstition"*, *"Fortune-Telling"*, and *"Xolida Practices Fortune-Telling"* expose the harms of unscientific beliefs, discouraging practices like consulting fortune-tellers or relying on spiritual healers for medical treatment. Ayni effectively highlights the dangers of religious dogma and superstition, a perspective that remains relevant today.

Ayni also emphasizes the importance of physical health. The chapters *"Maintaining Health"*, *"Ways to Stay Healthy"*, and *"Xolida Falls Ill"* are dedicated to this subject.

He argues that the foundation of a good life is good health, which requires proper nutrition, drinking clean boiled water, maintaining hygiene, regularly washing, and avoiding bad habits. Although his understanding of health was influenced by the limited medical knowledge of his time, his advice on hygiene and cleanliness remains valuable.

In the chapter "*Xolida's Library*", Ayni portrays Xolida as a passionate reader who eagerly builds her personal library and shares knowledge with her community. This depiction aims to instill a love for books and learning among readers.

In "*Famous Women*", Xolida reads about prominent female figures in history who, despite religious and societal restrictions, became poets, writers, and artists. Inspired by their courage, Xolida aspires to contribute positively to society. Through this, Ayni demonstrates the power of books in shaping young minds and encouraging them to pursue meaningful goals.

Through "*Qiz bola yoxud Xolida*", Ayni reaffirms his reputation as an esteemed educator and an advocate of enlightenment. The novel presents his valuable insights on teaching methodologies, character development, and the significance of education in shaping responsible and capable individuals. Ultimately, Ayni's work serves as a guide for raising disciplined, socially conscious, and skilled young people.

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